

**LANGUAGE SKILLS AND EXPOSURE TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE
AMONG BACHELOR OF ARTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE
STUDIES STUDENTS AT MINDANAO STATE
UNIVERSITY- SULU**

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Language Skills and Exposure to English Language Among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies Students at Mindanao State University- Sulu

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Abstract

The language proficiency and exposure to the English language among Mindanao State University-Sulu students pursuing a Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies (BA ELS) are the subjects of this descriptive study. It covers the age, gender, and year level demographic profiles of the respondents, as well as the level of language proficiency and exposure to English among MSU-Sulu's BA ELS students. Additionally, it addresses the noteworthy variations in language proficiency and exposure to English language among MSU-Sulu's BA ELS students when data are organized based on their age, gender, and academic year, as well as the noteworthy associations between the subcategories that fall under the umbrella of language proficiency and exposure to English language among BA ELS students at MSU-Sulu. MSU-Sulu was the site of the study. The BA ELS students at MSU-Sulu are the study's responders. The study's respondents were chosen through the application of purposeful sampling. There are two components to the research tool. The respondents' age, gender, and year level are all included in Part I's demographic profile. Thirteen assertions about language proficiency and nine statements about exposure to the English language make up Part II. There are five (5) options available, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." The majority of the BA ELS students are female and in their first year of college, meaning that they are the appropriate age for their current year level. In terms of exposure to and level of language competency in English, the respondents agree. There isn't any noticeable difference in the demographic profile. There is a strong correlation between language proficiency and exposure to English.

Keywords: *skills, language, studies, students, proficiency*

Introduction

Language is the medium of exchange for ideas, emotions, and information in communication. However, studies have shown that learning many languages offers benefits for cognitive function throughout the lifespan (Bialystok, Craik & Ryan, 2016), and estimates suggest that half of the world's population knows more than one language (Grosjean & Miller, 1994). These days, speaking English is thought to be essential for communicating with people worldwide. A solid command of the English language is necessary for improving one's job, education, and social position, claims Charisma (2016). In the Philippines, both public and private schools have adopted ESL/EFL programs in an effort to give the younger generation the English communication skills necessary for both higher education and career opportunities. Learning a language can be both a difficult and rewarding undertaking, particularly for those who are learning it as a second or foreign language. Given the importance of English, the Department of Education (DepEd) has declared that pupils need to acquire it as a foreign language. It has received a great deal of attention in the Philippines, especially in the field of education. Six (6) years of continuous instruction is the standard length of elementary basic education in the Philippines. Secondary education, which was implemented during President Benigno C. Aquino's late 15th term, lasts for an additional two (2) years following the initial four (4) years of this six-year period. Secondary school is not mandatory, but students who wish to pursue academic or career goals can enroll in a two-year course of sequential study, which typically starts at age 12. Depending on the specialized track they have selected, students may take the Alternative Learning System (ALS) general secondary certificates test after completing this two-year curriculum. Students who pass the exam are given a specific certificate. Students may begin applying to universities as soon as they have completed this course of study. (General rules for secondary Stage and English curriculum guidelines, MOE, 1993).

Exposure to language, on the other hand, describes how language learners engage with the language they attempt to learn. Giving pupils enough opportunities to practice the language in a variety of settings with a diversity of speakers is one of the most crucial things a teacher does in the classroom. Not only can teachers employ natural language input from media like books, magazines, cassettes, movies, internet, and television, but they can also provide real-world examples of language use since they are qualified speakers of the language. As a general rule, encounters outside of the classroom are referred to as language exposure. Benson (2017) defines outside-of-class language exposure as "any kind of learning that takes place outside the classroom and involves self-instruction, self-directed naturalistic learning, or naturalistic learning outside of the classroom." Engaging in face-to-face conversations with native English speakers (L2 interaction), using the English language in daily situations, accessing the internet in English, reading English-language publications, and watching English-language television shows and movies are a few examples of language exposure outside of the classroom.

English language learning is said to require to be encouraged both within and outside of the classroom by employing the appropriate tactics. The target language proficiency and English language proficiency of the students are enhanced by these techniques. But because these activities require artistic talent and creative capabilities, the researcher is not talking about writing plays or stories with pupils who do not speak English well. The only thing that teachers can hope for is that when their students get some exposure to the English

language, they will be able to speak easily and at a natural level.

As exposure to language boosts learners' chances of acquiring the language more quickly and successfully, language acquisition experts actually concur that language exposure is essential for language learning. Since learning can occur anywhere and at any time, a student's exposure to a language is considered successful when they are able to produce it. If pupils focus solely on classroom activities, it is doubtful that they will learn a foreign or second language. While many students learn English in the classroom, without opportunities for outside practice, they will not acquire the language correctly.

It should be emphasized that exposure can improve a target language directly, which means that social interaction with speakers of the target language can advance language ability. Boyle and Peregoy (2006). However, a lack of exposure to the target language may be caused by the learner's fear and sense of self-efficacy, especially when it comes to speaking and writing. Students studying, for instance, in a country where English is the official language are more likely to be exposed to and ultimately acquire the language. In addition to employing authentic resources like CDs, movies, television, websites, magazines, and books, a teacher who speaks the language well can also give pupils examples of language use in everyday situations.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to ascertain the level of exposure to and language proficiency among English language studies bachelor's degree students at Mindanao State University (MSU) in Sulu during the academic year 2023–2024. It specifically responded to the following queries:

1. What is the demographic profile of student-respondents in term of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender; and
 - 1.3 year level?
2. What is the extent of Language Skills and Exposure to English Language among BA ELS students at MSU-Sulu?
3. Is there any significant difference in the extent of Language Skills and Exposure to English Language among BA ELS students at MSU-Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of:
 - 3.1 age;
 - 3.2 gender; and
 - 3.3 year level?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Language Skills and Exposure to English Language among BA ELS students at MSU-Sulu?

Literature Review

Acknowledge that acquiring a second language, also referred to as a foreign language (L2), is crucial for improving first language acquisition. Speaking, reading, writing, and listening are not the only skills that need to be taught when teaching language, according to Darancik (2018). Developing and reinforcing these four basic language skills according to the needs and proficiency of the students is essential for effective and successful education and training in foreign language courses. The study's goal is to identify the main concerns around the subject by finding out how foreign language learners often approach the four basic language skills as well as their ideas about feelings and thoughts.

The task is not to defend or oppose the inclusion of the four essential skills in foreign language training, but rather to show how students approach and acquire these competencies. This is a qualitative study that employed data from university students majoring in foreign language instruction that was collected using a questionnaire that asked them about their perceptions of the four basic language talents. The results of the study show that speaking is the skill that students think they need to work on the most, find the hardest, and wish they could do better at. Students will be more receptive to learning and more successful in their academic pursuits if they can accurately hear, understand, and speak a foreign language. This illustrates how important verbal communication skills are and how different approaches must be used while acquiring them in foreign language training.

In order to better understand how English teachers in grades 7-9 focus on various language skills during instruction, Markström (2019) conducted a study. To do this, there are several questions to respond to. First, which language skills are most important, according to research and advice documents? The second question focuses on what language skills teachers think are most important and whether or not they teach these skills in-depth. The last question is: Why should educators stress specific language proficiency? The fourth issue concerns the ways that the teachers use to teach these linguistic talents. The communicative approach, in particular, offers solutions to these issues in theories of teaching English as a foreign language. Previous research indicates that mastery of the English language calls for all abilities. However, the interview results show that the teachers place more importance on writing, reading, and, to a lesser extent, listening. The reason the professors say this is that these are the talents that the students struggle with the most. In addition, several methods that outline how specific language skills could be taught are provided. The language skills that are learned include speaking, writing, listening, and reading. The results were derived from semi-structured quantitative interviews with teachers who worked at a specific school. Several conclusions have been drawn from the theoretical framework and the teachers' answers. This study found a difference between the language skills teachers actually teach and the language skills they believe are most important.

Many adult Filipino migrants, or overseas Filipino workers, find it challenging to learn the language of their new nation, according to Meniado (2019). This study examines the methods by which these workers acquire their second languages (L2) and the variables that impact both their rate and effectiveness in language acquisition. The objective is to create a second language acquisition that could be useful in creating welfare and training programs for adults that are responsive. This study demonstrates how immersion and actual use of the target language in authentic communicative contexts can aid in language acquisition. It used a mixed methods research design and 15 Filipino overseas workers as samples who learned various local languages in ten different host countries.

The findings of this study add credence to the idea that L2 learning can be accelerated by employing an instrument, integrative motivation, and strong support from the target language (TL) community, even though aging and the absence of a requirement for L2 at work can slow down the process overall. In terms of communication techniques, direct appeals to authority (native speakers) are employed after gestures, facial expressions, and translation technology. Their desire to become bilingual stems from their employment, desire to integrate into the culture, and awareness of their status as foreign employees. The significance of the findings for teaching adult language learners and foreign workers second languages are discussed.

According to Sadiku (2015), teaching and learning are the two basic processes that support today's activities for both instructors and students. Along with teaching and requiring what it teaches, the learning process also aligns the interests of the instructor and the learner. It's becoming more and more crucial for students to be able to educate themselves and gain the abilities required for independent work by utilizing the most advanced, conscious, sustainable, active, and creative learning strategies. Understanding the significance of using skills during class time is the aim of this topic. The teacher is free to use a variety of teaching and learning strategies to suit the needs of the students in different classes. As the student's verbal skill and independence increase and the procedure becomes more consistent, he incorporates different teaching methods and modifies it as needed. Teaching is centered on communication techniques, task-based learning, functional methods, real-world examples, etc. Based on the language skills (hearing, speaking, reading, and writing), different strategies and processes are employed to put these methods into practice. To plan and organize teaching, teachers and students collaborate. To enhance teaching and learning, the instructor finds efficient ways to organize communication activities and provides materials that students can use. In addition to teaching, instructors in modern schools often carry out supervisory responsibilities. Together, they forge cooperative partnerships as they study. Clarification is provided by the instructor, who also evaluates the students' understanding of the material. This means outlining the rules for the industry as well as the roles that students have in the various activities. In addition to helping students use a range of information technology tools both within and outside of the classroom, the teacher promotes and supports the usage of electronic and audiovisual resources. According to the age-appropriate educational criteria, students are granted access to the website. Based on the learning objectives, all four language skills techniques should be applied in ascending degrees within a teaching hour. By putting the pupils in the spotlight, you can encourage active language use and get them ready for a new stage of their education or to meet demands of labor market.

In order to determine how students' exposure to the English language at home, in the media, and through technology helps them understand English courses, Soriano and Garcia (2021) carried out a qualitative study. Out of three groups in Grade 10, fifteen students were specifically selected. An earlier interview, conducted before the selection procedure, chose responders from among the students who could compute their notions with clarity. Their answers to a series of questions posed to them during the Focus Group Discussion were examined using the deductive research approach. The results of the study showed how exposure to the English language in the media, on technology, and at home helps kids develop their vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation skills—all of which they utilize in their English classes and which eventually help with their comprehension of the language. This study has so shown that exposure to the English language helps students understand the material they are learning in English classes.

Everyday interactions with the English language occur for learners. While motivation and interest play a significant role in language learning, it's critical to make a distinction between work and reward when incorporating different media into the classroom. When education takes place in a classroom, pupils can recognize when they are being instructed and can concentrate on what the teacher is teaching. Nonetheless, they might learn new words and phrases that they might use in regular discussions when they watch a movie or play a game on their home computer. This means that learning occurs incidentally (d'Ydewalle & De Bruycker, 2007).

Consequently, regular classroom training is one method to acquire and use a new language skill, even if there are several opportunities to study a language outside of the classroom. Students can benefit from group work, projects, and multimedia (Internet, social media, TV, radio, and video games) to help them develop the target language in the proper methods.

Students' failure to learn the English language can be attributed to a variety of reasons, including the curriculum design, the teacher, practice, interest, and teaching approach. Despite English's well-known global reputation and continuous use in both national and international contexts, not much research on exposure to the language and language learning has been done or published.

Since most children are not exposed to adequate real-world English-speaking contexts or opportunities to interact in the language, their learning can only be enhanced in the classroom through rigorous training. Despite having studied English in the classroom, many pupils have never utilized it outside of it. They struggle greatly to acquire the language because they lack the confidence to talk confidently in English. Precious Domingo (2019): Assessing the level of language exposure that Visayas State University students have had in relation to their English language acquisition was the goal of this study. An individual's ability to acquire a language is influenced by their exposure to the target language. Using a modified language exposure questionnaire, the researcher identified the activities that

exposed students to the target language. By applying a scoring system, the researcher was able to determine the extent of the pupils' exposure to English. Most of the participants have a moderate level of language exposure, according to the study's findings. Students spend the majority of their time in English-speaking environments—at school or through other media—as opposed to at home or with friends. This outcome can be used by educators and learners to engage in activities that increase English language learning both within and outside of the classroom.

Finally, previous studies have shown that exposure to the English language has positive effects on language learning. But acquiring a language is necessary to become proficient in a second or foreign language, and exposure to the target language can offer a helpful and positive learning environment. According to these research, a variety of media can have a favorable effect on the language development of ESL/EFL students. Media can be a useful tool for learning a second language, according to research conducted by many scholars. Still, a plethora of studies showed that language learning might be accelerated by explicit instruction—the kind that is often taught in classrooms.

Consequently, because so much is communicated in English, speaking with native speakers, watching English-language media, listening to English-language music, practicing English on social media, and searching the internet for information can all help expose students to the language.

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive-exploratory research design using a quantitative research method was used to realize the comprehensive architecture for the data gathering in this study. Carefully describing educational phenomena is the goal of descriptive research, a kind of quantitative inquiry (Gall, Gall & Borg, 2007).

The quantitative research approach, according to Burns and Grove (2005), is used to characterize variables, look at correlations between variables, and ascertain cause-and-effect interactions between variables.

In order to ascertain the level of language proficiency and exposure to the English language among Mindanao State University-Sulu students pursuing a Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies, the researcher used this particular design.

Participants

The respondents of this study were the Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. The assumption of the distribution of the respondents is shown in table 1.

Table 1. *Assumption of the distribution of respondents according to year level*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
First Year	8	30	38
Second Year	7	17	24
Third Year	3	20	23
Fourth Year	7	8	15
Total	25	75	100

Instruments

A modified questionnaire from Samer Mahmoud Al-Zoubi's research study served as the research instrument and was utilized to produce the results. The instrument has two (2) blocks in total. A questionnaire covering demographic information like age, gender, and year level was employed by the researcher in Block I. Additionally, block II of the questionnaire was utilized to gauge the respondents' level of exposure to and proficiency in the English language.

Procedure

In order to collect the data, the dean of Graduate Studies' letter of approval was requested. The chair of the department of languages at Mindanao State University-Sulu as well as the office of the dean of the college of arts and sciences both provided written consent requests to the researcher. The researcher personally gave the questionnaires to the study participants after receiving consent for the request.

Results and Discussion

In this section, Mindanao State University – Sulu Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies (BAELS) students' language proficiency and exposure to the language are discussed and the findings of the data acquisition are presented. Regarding age, gender, and year level of the student respondents, it addresses the demographic profiles of BAELS students at MSU - Sulu as well as the degree of language proficiency and exposure to English. Along with the significant differences in language proficiency and exposure to English among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu based on student demographics (age, gender, and year level), it also discusses the significant

correlation between the subcategories that fall under the umbrella of language proficiency and exposure to English among BAELS students at MSU-Sulu. At MSU-Sulu, the study was carried out. The MSU-Sulu BAELS students are the study's responders.

1. What is the socio - demographic profile of the student - respondents in terms of 1.1 age, 1.2 gender, and 1.3-year level?

1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.1 displays the age distribution of the respondents. Just 4% of the respondents are 17 years old or younger, and 80% of the respondents are each 20 years of age or older. The outcome suggests that over 50% of the participants have reached a mature age.

Table 1.1 *Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age*

Age	Frequency	Percentage
17 years old and below	4	4%
18 – 19 years old	16	16%
20 years old and above	80	80%
Total	100	100%

1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

The gender-specific demographic profile of the respondents is shown in Table 1.2. It revealed that just 26% of study participants were men and 74% of respondents were women. According to the results, women make up the majority of responders.

Table 1.2 *Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender*

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	26	26%
Female	74	74%
Total	100	100%

1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year Level

Table 1.3 gives the respondents' year-level demographic information. According to the data, 40% of the respondents are first-year students, and only 15% are fourth-year students. According to the results, nearly half of the respondents are first-year college students.

Table 1.3 *Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year Level*

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
1 st	40	40%
2 nd	23	23%
3 rd	22	22%
4 th	15	15%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the extent of language skills and exposure to English language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu?

Table 2.1 presents the extent of exposure to language skills among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu in terms of language skills.

Out of the results, there were only two statements that the respondents strongly agreed with: practicing English in different contexts outside of the classroom improves my English language proficiency (mean = 4.610, SD = .709), and exposure to the language helps me get good grades and a good job (mean = 4.590, SD = .637) [1]. The remaining statements, which included watching English-language TV, movies, or videos, speaking English outside of the classroom helps with language acquisition (mean = 4.460, SD = .717), and forcing oneself to speak English even when one is afraid of making a mistake (mean = 4.200, SD = .841), all demonstrated agreement. The average mean of 4.203 indicates that the respondents are somewhat exposed (agreeing) with the degree of exposure to language skills at MSU-Sulu. The outcome only suggests that English language proficiency was not always exposed to MSU-Sulu's BAELS students. Markström (2019) determined which abilities students are weak in in his research. Furthermore, several methods are provided that explain how specific language skills could be taught. Language skills are acquired by reading, writing, speaking, and listening. To get the answers, semi-structured quantitative interviews with teachers working at a specific school were conducted. Numerous conclusions have been drawn from the theoretical framework and the teachers' reactions. This study found a difference between the language skills instructors teach in the classroom and the language skills they believe are most important.

Table 2.1 *Extent of Exposure to Language Skills among BAELS Students at MSU – Sulu*

Language Skills	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Practicing English language outside the classroom in many contexts improve my English language level.	4.610	.709	Strongly Agree
2. Having more exposure to English language develops my proficiency in English language.	4.200	1.082	Agree
3. Doing English homework, assignments, and project work expands my English language.	3.960	.953	Agree
4. Encouraging myself to speak English even I am afraid of making a mistake.	4.200	.841	Agree
5. Exposing to English language helps me to get marks in exams and a good job.	4.590	.637	Strongly Agree

6. Watching English TV programmes, videos, or movies facilitates English language acquisition.	4.300	1.000	Agree
7. Watching a lot of English TV programmes, videos, or movies without subtitles in my own language helps me to understand English language better.	3.960	1.109	Agree
8. Using social media (Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram...) facilitates English language acquisition.	3.970	.881	Agree
9. Surfing the internet helps me in learning English language.	4.110	.840	Agree
10. Communications in English outside the classroom makes English language acquisition easy.	4.460	.717	Agree
11. Using English in real life situations increases my English fluency.	4.150	.908	Agree
12. Travelling to English speaking countries develops English language acquisition.	4.170	.858	Agree
13. Applying variety of techniques in the classroom by the teacher increases English language acquisition.	3.960	552	Agree
Average	4.203		Agree

4.50 – 5.00 Strongly Agree (expose extremely); 3.50 – 4.49 Agree (expose slightly); 2.50 – 3.49 Partially Agree (expose partially); 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree (don't expose); 1.00 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree (extremely don't expose)

Table 2.2 presents the extent of exposure to English language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu.

Only one item (mean = 3.330, SD = 1.326) was somewhat agreed with by the respondents, according to the results: writing clearly and systematically is aided by sending emails and doing research in English. The remaining claims, for which they expressed agreement, were as follows: First, listening to English-language programs and music improves my comprehension of the language on quizzes, assignments, and projects (mean = 4.490, SD = .703); second, it makes it easier for me to pronounce the language correctly (mean = 4.490, SD = 0.541). Based on a mean score of 3.961, BAELS students at MSU-Sulu agree (somewhat expose) on how much they are exposed to the English language. Simply said, the outcome suggests that MSU-Sulu's BAELS students weren't always exposed to English Language.

Soriano and (2021) found that by exposing kids to the English language via media, technology, and at home, they can enhance their proficiency in grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. They will be better able to understand the material being covered in English class with these abilities. Consequently, our study has shown that exposure to the English language can help students understand the material they are learning.

Table 2.2 Extent of Exposure to English Language among BAELS Students at MSU - Sulu

Exposure to English Language	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Listening to English programmes and songs helps me to understand English language better.	4.490	.703	Agree
2. Listening to English programmes and songs improves my English pronunciation.	4.490	.541	Agree
3. Talking face to face with English language native speakers is beneficial and enjoyable.	4.340	.807	Agree
4. Talking on the phone with English native speakers increases my English proficiency.	3.710	1.057	Agree
5. Talking with English language speakers helps me to overcome my grammatical errors.	4.120	.715	Agree
6. Reading English books, magazines, and newspapers increases my reading speed.	3.780	.917	Agree
7. Reading English books, magazines, and newspapers improves my vocabulary and spelling.	3.860	.900	Agree
8. Writing emails and research in English assists me to write in an organized way and neat handwriting.	3.330	1.326	Partially Agree
9. Writing down the new words I pick up when watching TV or using the internet, helps me to speak English fluently.	3.530	1.322	Agree
Average	3.961		Agree

4.50 – 5.00 Strongly Agree (expose extremely); 3.50 – 4.49 Agree (expose slightly); 2.50 – 3.49 Partially Agree (expose partially); 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree (don't expose); 1.00 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree (extremely don't expose)

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of language skills and exposure to English language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu when data are grouped according to age, gender, and year level?

3.1 By Gender

Table 3.1 shows the differences in the extent of language skills and exposure to English language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender. The t-test was used because there are only two groups for gender. The seal of approval. The p = value of .05. and the sig are lower than the English skills rating of 0.215. Similarly, the exposure to the English language value of 0.110 is greater than the 2-tailed, p=.05 tests. It indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted. There isn't any noticeable difference in the degree of language ability or exposure to When gender-based statistics are combined, English language competency among MSU-Sulu BAELS students is examined. According to the results, gender had no effect on the level of language exposure or proficiency among MSU-Sulu BAELS students.

Table 3.1 t – test for Significant Difference in the Extent of Language Skills and Exposure to English Language Among BAELS Students at MSU - Sulu in terms of Gender

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	t	Sig.	Description
English Skills	Male	4.450	.630	.220	18.490	.215	Not Significant
	Female	4.230	.750				

Exposure to English Language	Male	3.950	.550	.170	20.150	.110	Not Significant
	Female	3.780	.720				

Table 3.2 presents the significant difference in the extent of English skills and exposure to English language among BAELS Students at MSU - Sulu in terms of age and year level.

The seal of acceptance. value of 0.668 for the age and sign, respectively. The p-value of .05, is less than the year level value of 0.367. It indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There are no appreciable differences in the level of English ability and exposure to the language among MSU-Sulu's BAELS students when the data is sorted by year level and age.

The results imply that differences in the demographic characteristics of MSU - Sulu's BAELS students do not always correspond to differences in their exposure to or ability in the English language.

Focusing on the notion that babies often receive "impoverished" input from the adults in their surroundings, the study bolsters Chomsky's "Nativist Theory," which maintained that toddlers are predisposed to language acquisition. Adolescents are exposed to limited language usage, and people commonly employ poor grammar. It follows that for children to learn language, their brains must already include a linguistic framework that is triggered by the stimuli they come across. By mapping linguistic information and creating connections inside its universal grammar, a cognitive language learning apparatus can subsequently, in Chomsky's view, learn languages.

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in the Extent of Language Skills and Exposure to English Language Among BAELS Students at MSU - Sulu in terms of Age and Year Level

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig.	Description
Age	.117	3				
Between Groups	13.993	96	0.039	0.267	.668	Not Significant
Within Groups	14.110	99	0.146			
TOTAL						
Year Level	.216	2				
Between Groups	10.344	97	0.108	1.009	.367	Not Significant
Within Groups	10.560	99	0.107			
Total						

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of language skills and exposure to English language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu?

Pearson Product-Moment association, or Pearson r, was used to determine whether there is a significant correlation between the subcategories contained under the degree of language competency and exposure to the English language among MSU – Sulu BAELS students. A significant result of .05 for the two-tailed test indicated that there was a high correlation between the values of $r = 0.560$ for English skills and $r = 0.581$ for exposure to the language.

The results merely imply that the degree of English competence of MSU-Sulu BAELS students and their exposure to the language are significantly correlated. Differentiating between the two is difficult. They have ties to one another.

Students believe they need the most assistance and want to enhance their speaking abilities, according to Darancik's (2018) research. Students are more likely to be willing and successful in their studies when they are able to speak, hear, and understand a foreign language accurately. This illustrates how important verbal communication skills are and how different approaches must be used while acquiring them in foreign language training.

Table 4. Significant Correlation in the Extent of Language Skills and Exposure to English Language among BAELS Students at MSU – Sulu

		Pearson r	Sig.	n	Description
English Skills	Exposure to English Language	0.560	.000	100	High Correlation
Exposure to English Language	English Skills	0.581	.000	100	High Correlation

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at $E = .05$
 Correlation Scales adapted from Hopkins (2002):
 - 0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1 – 0.3 = Low; 0.3 – 0.5 = Moderate; 0.5 – 0.7 = High;
 0.7 – 0.9 = Very High; 0.9 – 1.0 = Nearly Perfect

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the following is concluded: MSU-Sulu first-year BAELS students make up the bulk of responders, and for their current year level, the BAELS students there are precisely the right age. The course is primarily attended by female students. MSU-Sulu's BAELS students agree that the more time they spend in the classroom and on campus, the more fluent their English will become.

The fact that their profiles regarding the extent of their exposure to and skill in the English language are identical shows that there is no correlation between the two: speaking the language and becoming proficient in it. Both are crucial to one another because of the substantial correlation that exists between exposure to the English language and English proficiency.

The study recommends the following: (1) To improve their English, English teachers should advise BAELS students to speak solely English in class. (2) To encourage pupils to follow suit and improve their English-speaking skills, English teachers should refrain from using code switching when instructing the subject. (3) In addition to speaking English with one another both inside and outside of the classroom, BAELS students should not simply rely on their teachers. (4) It is important to constantly remind BAELS students that speaking English is more important than just learning verb tenses. (5) To encourage students to read more and improve their English, the MSU-Sulu English Department should make every effort to obtain additional English-language reading resources.

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